

POLITÉCNICA

Development and application of bioinformatics tools for protein loop modelling

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ABSTRACT

Prediction of protein loop structures is crucial for protein structure modelling, structural refinement, antibody design, or ion channels modelling. Here we propose several methodological improvements to our loop modelling online service: Random Coordinate Descent (RCD+ <http://rcd.chaconlab.org/>). This server combines an *ab initio* loop closure algorithm with a full-atom refinement in Rosetta. We propose to include a novel knowledge-based pairwise potential (KORP) which takes into account information of the relative position and orientation per residue. The inclusion of KORP, a Ramachandran potential correction, and an extensive parameter optimization significantly improve the prediction accuracy of the loop modelling procedure. Moreover, superior efficiency has been achieved by drastically reducing the number of loop candidates to be further refined. The approach has been successfully validated with several standard loop benchmarks. Interestingly, promising results were obtained even in one of the most challenging applications scenarios: the H3 loops prediction of the antibody complementary determining regions.

INTRODUCTION

The 3D structure of a protein gives crucial information about its potential functions and interactions. The number of known protein structures included in the Protein Data Bank (PDB) are over 150 thousand (Berman et al., 2000). However, this figure is approximately three order of magnitude smaller than the number of identified protein sequences (about 156 million) available in UniProt (Universal Protein Resource) (C. H. Wu, 2005). Thus, the computational prediction of protein structures is constitutes one of the most challenging problems of current computational biology (Anfinsen, 1973)(Baker & Sali, 2001). One of the main challenges in this field is the prediction of the relatively short peptide segments linking two secondary structure elements, i.e. the protein loops.

Such structures are essential in ligand binding, molecular recognition, enzyme catalysis, or protein-protein and protein-nucleic acids interactions (S. J. Wu & Dean, 1996). Furthermore, loops prediction is also crucial to model the missing protein segments in experimental atomic structures.

Methods for loop structure prediction can be classified in 3 different groups: template-based, *ab initio* approaches and a mix of both. The *ab initio* methods generate feasible loop conformations from scratch while the template-based methods find the most similar model from a structural library of loops extracted from the PDB.

Although template-based methods generally achieve good predictions, they are only applicable when a template for the problem already exists. In contrast, *ab initio* methods overcome this limitation by performing an energy-based sampling of the conformational space. In this case, the major bottleneck is relative computational cost. The number of possible conformations increases

exponentially with the loop length and hence, the complexity of loop modelling prediction.

The first step for the *ab-initio* prediction of loops is to find geometrically feasible conformations between two given fixed residues. This problem is known as loop closure.

In our group, we have developed an *ab initio* loops prediction method that integrates loop closure, energy filtering, and detailed final refinement into the free web service RCD+ (rcd.chaconlab.org) (López-Blanco, Canosa-Valls, Li, & Chacón, 2016). This method comprises three steps:

- 1- **Generation of an ensemble of closed loops using Random Coordinate Descent (RCD)** (Chys & Chacón, 2013): The RCD generates closed loops in a very fast and efficient *ab initio* procedure (Fig. 1). The RCD iteratively moves the dihedral angles (ϕ and ψ) that are randomly selected within allowed threshold of Ramachandran distribution. This procedure is repeated until the requested number of loops is generated.

Fig. 1. Loop closure problem. A) An initial random conformation is first generated to find a geometrically feasible conformation for a missing short peptide segment between two fixed amino acid residues (or anchors). Then, the dihedral angles ϕ and ψ of the backbone are iteratively modified to connect to overlap its carboxy-terminal residue to the anchor target position. B) Illustrative protein case of an ensemble of closed loops generated by RCD (in blue)

- 2- **Scoring the ensemble of RCD closed loops:** The closed loops are ranked with the simple coarse-graining ICOSA potential (Elhefnawy, Chen, Han, & Li, 2015) to select the most energetically favorable conformations, i.e. those loops closer to the native.
- 3- **Refine best loops selected in the previous step with PyRosetta** (Chaudhury, Lyskov, & Gray, 2010): This final refinement includes the information of all the atoms as side chains looking to avoid possible collisions. The models with low energy according to Rosetta are selected as the final output of the entire algorithm.

We consider the two possible prediction scenarios: i) native, when the conformations of the side-chains of the loop environment are reliable, e.g. for predicting the missing loops in crystallographic structures, or ii) modeling, when the side-chains of the loop environment could be in a different conformation and should be modeled, e.g. for predicting loops in homology model.

To improve the results of the RCD, here, we first propose the substitution of the ICOSA potential in the scoring step for a more efficient recently developed potential: the Knowledge-based ORientational Potential (KORP) (López-Blanco & Chacón, 2019). Second, we proposed the incorporation of a Ramachandran term to strength the stereochemistry quality of the loops. Since the proposed changes can influence the large number of parameters, we performed an extensive optimization of them to guarantee maximum performance.

One of the most important applications inside loop modelling is the antibody modelling of H3 loops (C. Marks & Deane, 2017). Vertebrates have an adaptive immune system capable of developing antibody proteins against any antigenic particle. The structure of the antibodies is Y shaped, composed of two symmetrical chains (heavy and light). The complementary determining regions (CDR) are placed on each tip of the Y and are composed of six hypervariable loops (three in the heavy chain and three in the light chain): L1, L2, L3, H1, H2, and H3. The length and the amino acid sequence of these loops vary considerably between antibodies while the rest of the protein is highly conserved. This variation/diversity of the CDR loops is responsible for its ability to bind and interact with a group of molecules as diverse as the antigens. The H3 CDR loop is the major contributor to the specificity of the interaction (Mian, Bradwell, & Olson, 1991). Contrary to other CDR loops, H3 has a huge scattering in the distribution of its sizes and shapes,

between 3 and 20 amino acids (Chothia & Lesk, 1987). Another attribute that makes H3 exceptional is that it can have two distinct conformations near the beginning of the loop: a kinked or extended structure. The kinked structure is the most abundant in H3. Within the loop prediction, the CDR, especially the H3 loops, have been continuously resisting (C. Marks & Deane, 2017) (Zhu & Day, 2013) (Claire Marks et al., 2017).

In this paper, we present and validate an improved version of RCD, as a preliminary application, we show the promising results obtained in the H3 prediction scenario.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

KORP 6D

KORP is a 6D, knowledge-based, pairwise and coarse-grained potential for proteins that depends on the relative position and orientation between residues (López-Blanco & Chacón, 2019). It considers a minimalist representation of three backbone atoms (C_α , C and N) and a single frame per pair of interacting residues i and j (Fig. 2). The C_α is the central atom to evaluate the relative distance (r_{ij}), and C and N are required to compute the polar (θ_i , θ_j , φ_i , φ_j) and dihedral (ω_{ij}) angles.

Fig. 2. KORP parameters: Schematic view defining the relative orientation and position of two interacting residues and the description of the parameters involved as is defined in the original paper (López-Blanco & Chacón, 2019). r_{ij} is the distance between the two residues. ω_{ij} is the dihedral angle of the r_{ij} . θ_i , θ_j , φ_i and φ_j are the polar angles that describe the relative orientation of each residue.

KORP is derived from known protein structures of the training data set using the classical inverse Boltzmann equation:

$$E_{ij} = -RT \ln \frac{P_{ab}^{obs}(r_{ij}, \varphi_i, \theta_i, \varphi_j, \theta_j, \omega_{ij}) + z}{P^{ref}(r_{ij}, \varphi_i, \theta_i, \varphi_j, \theta_j, \omega_{ij}) + z} \quad (1)$$

Where P_{ab}^{obs} is the joint probability at the given relative distance and orientation of observing two amino acids i and j of type a and b , respectively. P^{ref} is the reference probability obtained from the training data set. The reference probability is defined as the classical reference state (Samudrala & Moul, 1998) that simply averages over the 20 different amino acid types to represent the reference probability regardless of residue type. This overlooks the non-specific interactions while enhancing specific amino acid type contributions. The probabilities are approximated by binning the variables space. The distance range is divided into 10 bins to consider interactions between residues. We divided the angular space (θ and φ) into 36 equal-area bins using an equal-area tessellation approach (Beckers & Beckers, 2012) that generates a uniform sampling of the polar angles of 34° approximately. The ω angle was divided into 8 bins of 45° . The added z constant is a simple trick to prevent infinite values for very small probabilities and to improve the numerical stability for low-count statistics.

The final energy value is a linear combination of different terms:

$$E = f_l \sum_{n < s}^{n=2} E_{ij}^{local} + \sum_{n > s}^{n=s} E_{ij}^{non-local} + f_r \sum_{n=1} E_i^{rama} \quad (2)$$

The first two terms, defined as local and nonlocal interactions, take into account different interactions depending on the distance in the sequence (n) between the i -th and the j -th ($n = j - i$) residues. Where s is the threshold between local and nonlocal terms ($s=5$ in this work) and is a weighting factor of the local term. These two terms are computed using the previous Boltzmann equation.

As a novelty, we have added a new knowledge-based term that uses the Ramachandran distributions of Phi and Psi angles of Dunbrack (Ting et al., 2010) in the Boltzmann equation:

$$E_i^{rama} = -RT \ln \frac{P_{ab}^{obs}(\phi, \psi | L, C, R)}{P^{ref}(\phi, \psi | C)} \quad (3)$$

The Ramachandran distribution depends on the target amino acid and its neighbour amino acids; where $P_{ab}^{obs}(\phi, \psi | L, C, R)$ is the conditional probability that any central residue C with the neighbours L and R (Left and Right) has the ϕ and ψ angles; and, $P^{ref}(\phi, \psi | C)$ is the conditional probability that any central residue C has the ϕ and ψ angles. This new term contains f_r as its own weighting factor.

KORP ALTERNATIVES

The KORP potential has six dimensions and one interaction frame per residue. However, we have

developed some alternatives to customize the method for specific applications.

The first alternative is reducing the number of dimensions to represent each pair-wise residue interaction from six to three. This representation would be faster and sufficiently accurate for some cases. In contrast to 6D (Fig. 2), the 3D representation only considers the distance (r_{ij}) and the polar angles (θ and φ) of each interacting residue pair i and j :

$$E_{ij} = -RT \left[\ln \frac{P_{ab}^{obs}(r_{ij}, \varphi_i, \theta_i)}{P^{ref}(r_{ij}, \varphi_i, \theta_i)} + \ln \frac{P_{ab}^{obs}(r_{ij}, \varphi_j, \theta_j)}{P^{ref}(r_{ij}, \varphi_j, \theta_j)} \right] \quad (4)$$

Identical to the ICOSA energy (Elhefnawy et al., 2015), the six dimensions are indirectly contemplated when considering each interaction from the point of view of each interacting residue.

Likewise, in 6D, the relative contribution of the local and non-local energy terms is tuned by a weighting factor (f_i) as in equation 2. The Ramachandran term has not been implemented in 3D yet.

The second alternative is increasing the number of interaction frames per residue. Whereas the original single-frame model used in 6D-approach needs three backbone atoms (C_α , C and N) per residue (Fig. 2), the two different double-frame models tested here require more:

- A. **C $_\beta$ -O** model uses the triplets C_β -N-C and O - C_α - C , with C_β and O as atoms for distance evaluation, and N , C_α and C to compute polar angles.
- B. **O-N** model uses the triplets O - C_α - C and N - C_α - C_β , with O and N as atoms for distance evaluation, and C_α , C_β and C to compute polar angles.

KORP TRAINING DATA

1. Training data set

The known protein structure data used to generate the KORP potential was obtained from the PISCES web server (Wang & Dunbrack, 2003). It includes a total of 36.851 non-redundant protein chains having <90% sequence identity, along with a resolution better than 3.0 \AA , an R-factor below 0.25. To avoid over-training effects, all structures with sequence identity greater than or equal to 50% of the KORP test data structures were removed using CD-HIT (Fu, Niu, Zhu, Wu, & Li, 2012). The final training set included 35.929 protein chains.

2. Contact and potential maps

We obtained a total of approximately 250 million residue-residue contacts with the training set structures defined in the previous section. These contacts will be used to compute P^{ref} (equation 1).

In the first step, KORP process all the atoms of the given PDB and record in a binary file those contacts between atoms described by the frame that are inside two limit values (maximum and minimum radius). In the second step, KORP generates a potential map from the contact map as a function of the six potential parameters or dimensions.

KORP TEST DATA

1. Loop benchmarks

The benchmarks used for testing KORP in the optimization procedure are described in the previous KORP publication (López-Blanco & Chacón, 2019). These include datasets of loop length of 6, 8, 10 and 12 residues, each of them comprising 100 randomly selected targets. For each protein target case, we generated random ensembles of 10.000, 20.000, 50.000 and 100.000 geometric feasible loop decoys using our loop-closure algorithm RCD (Chys & Chacón, 2013). The loop length distribution of high-resolution proteins chains generated by the PISCES server indicates that 94% of loops are 12 or fewer residues long (Wang & Dunbrack, 2005), thus we fix the maximal loop size to 12. Also, notice that the number of decoys increases with length due to the higher conformational complexity.

2. Quality assessment metrics

To evaluate the discriminative performance of the potential energies (KORP and PyRosseta), we used the following metrics:

- **Top-RMSD X.** Average of the best RMSD decoy found in the X top decoys ranked by energy. Where X is either a percentage or an integer, e.g. X=1 is the RMSD of the lowest energy decoy and X=10% is the average RMSD of the top 10%.
- **LowE-Rank.** Rank average of the lowest energy decoy.

H3-CDR DATA

1. H3 benchmarks

The structures of benchmarks for the H3 modelling have been generated by others (see table 1 in (Weitzner & Gray, 2016)). This benchmark comprises 49 high quality crystallographic structures from human and mouse antibodies, with R-values lower than 0.2, resolution better than 2.5 Å and maximum B factor lower than 80.0 Å². This benchmark contains H3 loops with a length range between 9 and 19 residues. These structures were perturbed to simulate a real homology modelling situation. We substituted the H3 loop of the original homology model by the crystallographic one to compute the RMSD with the native conformation. The Perl script needed for this substitution and developed by me is

explained in *Supplementary text*. In addition to this homology modelling benchmark, we generate another benchmark from the original structures extracted for the PDB to perform test in more controlled scenarios.

2. H3 scenarios

The validation of the KORP has been performed with three different loop prediction scenarios:

- Native:** The crystallographic benchmark with native PyRosetta refinement. It is the easiest situation, when the loop environment, backbone and side-chains are reliable, e. g. missing loops prediction in a crystallographic structure.
- High quality modelling:** The crystallographic benchmark with modelling PyRosetta refinement. Moderate situation, when the backbone is reliable, but side-chains are not, e.g. Structures obtained by high homology modelling methods (90%).
- Medium quality modelling:** The modelling benchmark with modelling PyRosetta refinement. The most difficult situation, when the backbone and side-chains are perturbed, e.g. Structures obtained by medium homology modelling methods (50%).

3. Parsing Chothia antibody format into RCD input

The RCD needs a sequential numeration of the residues of the protein to operate. However, for historical reasons, antibodies PDBs have inconsistencies in the residue numbering used to identify the CDR loops. To solve such inconsistencies, we generated a Perl script to renumber the PDB typically in Chothia format (Al-Lazikani, Lesk, & Chothia, 1997) to conform the sequential RCD input (see *Supplementary text*).

RESULTS

KORP PARAMETER OPTIMIZATION IN 6D

Table 1. 6D KORP optimization

Parameters	Original set	Tested values	Optimal set
Max radius (Å)	16	17, 16, 15, 14, 13, 12	14
Min radius (Å)	3	2, 3, 4	3
N° radius bins	10	-	10
N° θ and ϕ bins	36	-	36
N° ω bins	8	-	8
Local limit (s)	4	-	4
Local factor (f_l)	1.8	1.5, 1.8, 2	1.8
Rama factor (f_r)	-	3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 10, 15, 20	6

The main objective is the characterization of a set of parameters for KORP to improve its near-native loop discrimination. The original, tested and optimal selected values of the parameters are in *Table 1* *Table 1*

To select the best parameter set we tested all possible combinations of parameters prioritizing consensus improvement, i.e. changes are considered only if the improvement is consistently detected in all the ensemble tests.

The most significant changes have been obtained by varying the values of the weight factors of the energy terms (f_i and f_r). In the majority of the parameters, the improvement was marginal or very small. For example, the variation of the radius did not report differences. Radius, θ , φ , and ω bins and local limit were already optimized in the KORP paper (López-Blanco & Chacón, 2019). Finally, the optimized and original parameters were compared in *Supp. Table 1*.

Fig. 3. KORP improvement in the 6 and 12 loops length benchmarks with a 99% RCD Ramachandran value: Comparison of the mean value of the best RMSD found in ranked decoys by KORP as the number of decoys taken into account increases between the old (blue) and new (red) set of parameters in a 10 replica experiment.

Since the RCD loop closure is a stochastic process, we repeated the loop and energy evaluation 10 times. In *Fig. 3*, the evolution of the mean and standard deviation of the best decoy RMSDs are shown as increasing the top selected decoys for the 6 and 12 residues benchmarks. As it can be seen, we obtained significant improvements in the top 0.1-20% (i.e. 1-200‰) and 0.1-2% (1-20‰) for 6 and 12 residues loops, respectively. These improvements

are more evident in lower Top-RMSDs percentages. For example, in the Top-RMSD 0.2% the gap between the original and optimal set is 0.1 Å and 0.05% for 6 and 12 residues, respectively. Similar results can be seen with 8 and 10 residues loops (see *Supp. Fig 1*).

KORP PARAMETER OPTIMIZATION IN 3D

Despite the proposed 6D representation naturally captures the relative orientation between two residues; a simple 3D representation would be faster and could be accurate enough for some applications. To test fairly, 3D vs 6D, we also explore and optimize the potential parameters like in the 6D case (see *Error! Not a valid bookmark self-reference.*).

Table 2. 3D KORP optimization

Parameters	Tested values	Optimal set
Max radius (Å)	16	16
Min radius (Å)	3	10
Nº radius bins	5, 10, 20, 50	50
Nº θ and φ bins	20, 50, 100, 200, 500, 1000	500
Local limit (s)	4	4
Local factor (f_l)	0, 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, 5, 10	1.5

The best results in 3D were obtained with a higher number of radial and angular bins with respect to the 6D approach. However, the total number of map cells is comparatively much smaller. While the 6D potential map has around 42 million cells, the 3D is 4 times smaller. Despite the simplicity of the 3D approach, the results were slightly but significantly worse than in 6D. In all the benchmarks, the Top-RMSDs with the optimal parameters were 0.10-0.15 Å worse (see *Supp. Table 1*).

The original KORP-6D employs one interaction frame per residue (see Materials and Methods). However, by considering more frames, the results could be improved at the expense of an increased map size and speed reduction. As a proof of concept, we tested the two double-frame models (see Materials and Methods) with the same 3D optimized parameters. KORP evaluation algorithm is not optimized for more than one frame and this multiple frame model takes 1000 times more time per loop and required high disc and RAM memory resources. This precluded the testing of multiple frameworks with 12 residue long loops.

In the C_{β} -O model, the Top-RMSDs improved around 0.1 Å with respect to the single frame model and reached the 6D optimal results for the 6 residues loop. However, as the loop size increases, this improvement is reduced to only 0.02 Å with respect to 3D and between 0.15 and 0.05 Å worse in comparison with the optimal 6D. On the contrary, the results of the O-N model were always equal or

Fig. 4 Best RMSD of the Top 10 energy structures generated and ranked by PyRosetta for all H3 loops and scenarios. The PDBs are sorted and colored by loop size.

worse than all the previous analysed situations. The results are shown in *Supp. Table 1*. Considering that the gain is marginal and the higher computational cost, the multiple framework setups has been discarded as the 3D version before.

KORP 6D VALIDATION WITH H3 LOOPS

We validated the optimized KORP 6D in the three different modelling scenarios using the H3 loop benchmarks. To this end, first, we generated 500.000 decoys for all H3 loop lengths with RCD loop closure method. Next, the top 0.2%, i.e. the first 1.000 decoys ranked by the optimized KORP energy, were refined and ranked in PyRosetta. In the *Fig. 4* we show the Top-RMSD 10 values, sorted by size and scenario. In the *Supp. Fig 2*, the Top-RMSDs 1, 2, and 5 are also shown.

The native scenario shows excellent results. All the loops with less than 16 residues except one have Top-RMSD 10 below 2 Å and most of them below 1 Å. In the high quality modelling scenario, the results were slightly worse and only 3 cases with less than 16 residues have a Top-RMSD 10 above 2 Å. In the most challenging, medium quality modelling scenario, as expected, the results are significantly worse, although the 60% of the loops smaller than 16 residues maintained Top-RMSD 10 below 2 Å. The final PyRosetta energy and RMSD for the 1.000 decoys previously selected by KORP (top 0.2%) are displayed in *Fig. 5A* for each scenario and three representative cases. The results for all the H3 loops cases are available in *Supp. Fig 3* (native), *Supp. Fig 4* (high quality modelling), and *Supp. Fig 5* (medium quality modelling).

Fig. 5 A) Representation of RMSD and energy of the 1000 loop decoys (grey) refined by PyRosetta in three proteins (*1dlf*, *2ypv* and *4nzu*) in the three scenarios: Native, High quality modelling and Medium quality modelling. The 10 best energy decoys are highlighted in yellow. **B)** Protein *1dlf* in the medium quality modelling scenario (white) with the native loop (green) and the best prediction model in the top 10 energy decoys (yellow). **C)** Protein *2ypv* in the medium quality modelling scenario (white) with the native loop (green) and the best prediction model in the top 10 energy decoys (yellow).

In the illustrative case of *1dlf* (12 residues) the top 10 decoys are the closest to the native in all scenarios. In other less frequent situations, e.g. as *2ypv* (12 residues), we obtained good modelling results in the native and high quality modelling scenarios but worsen in the more challenging medium quality modelling scenario. In the latter, the backbone environment of the predicted loop is inaccurate and prevents the achievement of a better conformation in the final PyRosetta refinement step. Unfortunately, for very big loops (16 residues or more), as *4nzu* (18 residues), the prediction typically fails in all the scenarios. In these cases, the conformational space is huge and even the half a million conformations initially sampled by RCD are not enough to find a single near native decoy.

DISCUSSION

A good discriminative potential in the scoring step is the key of the entire RCD loop modelling method. Since the full-atom refinement of PyRosetta step is the computational bottleneck, ideally, we need to consider the small number of closed loops possible but closest enough to the native in order to get good modelling results. Conversely, if we processed the entire loop ensemble generated by RCD with PyRosetta it will be almost impracticable. Thus, we need to find a sufficiently small ensemble of loops to

be refined in a reasonable amount of time, but containing enough close to the native loops.

The incorporation of KORP potential clearly improves near-native decoy discrimination than original ICOSA potential (López-Blanco & Chacón, 2019). KORP, and in particular the proposed new Ramachandran term consistently improved all the metrics. For example, 0.1 Å improvements in Top-RMSDs were regularly obtained for the shorter loops (6-8 residues long), but longer loops (10-12) still have consistent differences of 0.05 Å. Thus, the optimized KORP reduces the number of top energy ranked decoys to be refined by PyRosetta. While ICOSA used top 10%, KORP can use 0.2% obtaining better results. The employ of lower selection percentages, permits much larger sampling and hence improve prediction accuracy.

To extend the applicability range we tested some alternatives as the reduction of the dimensions and the increase of the consider frames. Unfortunately, these alternatives were discarded. The reduction of the dimensions, from 6D to 3D, only was marginally effective with length loop of 6 residues. Similar results have obtained using multiple-frames. In this case, the huge memory and computational cost prevent its use.

The application of the improved RCD modelling approach was carried out in different real modelling scenarios using antibody H3 loops. We obtained very

promising results in the loops with less than 16 amino acids even in modelling scenarios. The obtained results are competitive to the state-of-the-art methods (Weitzner & Gray, 2016). We obtain results of the same or better quality in many cases, but using only a fraction of time. This new version of RCD can model H3 loops from minutes to less than two hours, by contrast Rosetta Antigen-Antibody loop modelling protocol can take even several days on multiprocessors. The inclusion of KORP and the extensive parameter optimization significantly

improve the prediction accuracy of the RCD server that currently is the fastest alternative to generate very accurate loop predictions.

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Supplementary Materials

SUPPLEMENTARY TEXT

PERL SCRIPTS

For the correct working of the method, two main scripts have been developed in Perl language. Both scripts can be found in the following Github link: <https://github.com/ivanmartinhernandez/TFM>.

1. insertH3pdb.pl

This script needs two antibodies PDB files with the heavy (H) chain and the name of the output PDB as input. The first PDB given should be crystallographic and the second, the model. The script finds the atoms belonging to the H3 loop in the first PDB and replaces them in the second. This chimeric structure is written in the previously named PDB.

2. AB_numbering_reverse.pl

This script performs two actions simultaneously. First, it takes all the PDB structures that are in the executing directory and converts it from the Chothia format to the standard RCD input. Second, it generates a file text with all the information of the CDR loops for running the RCD directly. It is mandatory that all the input structures have Chothia format, otherwise, if there is some initial structure that does not comply, the program will crash. The Chothia format presents a series of inconsistencies in the numbering, by having some insertion or deletion in the CDR regions that allows starting and ending the CDR loops regardless of its variable length. However, there is a special field inside the PDB format that allows identifying different residues which have the same number. This script identifies every residue and gives it a consecutive number while writing in a file the sequence, and the new start and end residue number of the CDR loops.

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES

Supp. Fig 1. **KORP improvement in all the loops benchmarks with a 90% and 99% RCD Ramachandran value: A: loop size = 6, B: loop size = 8, C: loop size = 10 and D: loop size = 12.** On top: the comparison of the mean value of the best RMSD found in ranked decoys by KORP as the number of decoys taken into account increases between the old (blue) and new (red) set of parameters in a 10 replica experiment. On bot: the difference between set in each replica experiment in the same conditions (yellow).

Supp. Fig 2 Best RMSD of the Top 1, 2, 5 and 10 energy structures generated and ranked by PyRosetta for all H3 loops and scenarios. The PDBs are sorted and colored by loop size.

Supp. Fig 3 Native scenario. Representation of RMSD and energy of the 1000 loop decoys (grey) refined by PyRosetta in all the proteins of H3 benchmark in the Native scenario. The 10 best energy decoys are highlighted in yellow.

Supp. Fig 4. High quality modelling scenario. Representation of RMSD and energy of the 1000 loop decoys (grey) refined by PyRosetta in all the proteins of H3 benchmark in the High quality modelling scenario. The 10 best energy decoys are highlighted in yellow.

Supp. Fig 5. **Medium quality modelling scenario.** Representation of RMSD and energy of the 1000 loop decoys (grey) refined by PyRosetta in all the proteins of H3 benchmark in the Medium quality modelling scenario. The 10 best energy decoys are highlighted in yellow.

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLES

Supp. Table 1 **Quality assessment metrics** for KORP results of the original 6D parameter set, the optimized 6D parameter set, the optimized 3D parameter set the double-frame C-O set and the double-frame O-N set for each loop benchmark.

Length loops: 6 - 10.000 decoys per loop									Length loops: 10 - 50.000 decoys per loop								
RCD RAMA = 99									RCD RAMA = 99								
	LowE-RMSD	LowE-Rank	0.1%	0.2%	0.5%	1.0%	5.0%	10.0%		LowE-RMSD	LowE-Rank	0.1%	0.2%	0.5%	1.0%	5.0%	10.0%
Original 6D	1.478	1436.130	0.905	0.793	0.693	0.608	0.501	0.463	Original 6D	2.789	5858.720	1.365	1.290	1.170	1.100	0.993	0.966
Optimized 6D	1.351	1279.300	0.844	0.731	0.627	0.568	0.469	0.443	Optimized 6D	2.825	4684.540	1.346	1.264	1.151	1.094	0.995	0.963
Optimized 3D	1.479	1500.750	0.944	0.850	0.686	0.582	0.490	0.456	Optimized 3D	3.357	6308.260	1.461	1.359	1.233	1.155	1.020	0.985
2 frames (C-O)	1.335	937.830	0.802	0.722	0.605	0.549	0.447	0.431	2 frames (C-O)	2.937	5675.550	1.444	1.353	1.211	1.126	1.015	0.969
2 frames (O-N)	1.572	1065.830	0.955	0.805	0.657	0.577	0.463	0.439	2 frames (O-N)	3.133	6062.350	1.499	1.388	1.249	1.160	1.022	0.985
RCD RAMA = 90									RCD RAMA = 90								
	LowE-RMSD	LowE-Rank	0.1%	0.2%	0.5%	1.0%	5.0%	10.0%		LowE-RMSD	LowE-Rank	0.1%	0.2%	0.5%	1.0%	5.0%	10.0%
Original 6D	1.409	1863.350	0.877	0.809	0.683	0.626	0.515	0.486	Original 6D	2.734	6035.220	1.407	1.235	1.138	1.070	0.941	0.919
Optimized 6D	1.222	1745.470	0.828	0.756	0.653	0.597	0.502	0.475	Optimized 6D	2.854	5391.740	1.362	1.279	1.131	1.056	0.995	0.911
Optimized 3D	1.375	1949.600	0.894	0.794	0.688	0.637	0.496	0.467	Optimized 3D	3.044	7495.550	1.470	1.327	1.175	1.072	0.961	0.934
2 frames (C-O)	1.248	1388.190	0.818	0.741	0.628	0.572	0.481	0.460	2 frames (C-O)	2.950	5822.580	1.423	1.315	1.203	1.127	0.975	0.930
2 frames (O-N)	1.417	1687.240	0.849	0.758	0.658	0.601	0.499	0.467	2 frames (O-N)	2.895	6398.350	1.508	1.380	1.258	1.155	0.980	0.938
Length loops: 8 - 20.000 decoys per loop									Length loops: 12 - 100.000 decoys per loop								
RCD RAMA = 99									RCD RAMA = 99								
	LowE-RMSD	LowE-Rank	0.1%	0.2%	0.5%	1.0%	5.0%	10.0%		LowE-RMSD	LowE-Rank	0.1%	0.2%	0.5%	1.0%	5.0%	10.0%
Original 6D	2.044	1511.510	1.072	0.974	0.837	0.782	0.701	0.677	Original 6D	3.903	12680.650	1.611	1.505	1.375	1.298	1.199	1.177
Optimized 6D	1.966	1323.900	0.992	0.918	0.835	0.786	0.690	0.670	Optimized 6D	3.793	10628.900	1.582	1.459	1.358	1.297	1.176	1.165
Optimized 3D	2.398	1806.430	1.174	1.040	0.909	0.846	0.725	0.694	Optimized 3D	3.974	13349.370	1.624	1.521	1.415	1.347	1.220	1.176
2 frames (C-O)	2.013	1479.790	1.150	1.028	0.886	0.830	0.706	0.683									
2 frames (O-N)	2.129	1671.560	1.242	1.099	0.973	0.873	0.726	0.676									
RCD RAMA = 90									RCD RAMA = 90								
	LowE-RMSD	LowE-Rank	0.1%	0.2%	0.5%	1.0%	5.0%	10.0%		LowE-RMSD	LowE-Rank	0.1%	0.2%	0.5%	1.0%	5.0%	10.0%
Original 6D	1.904	2361.250	1.072	0.972	0.861	0.797	0.694	0.659	Original 6D	3.509	11630.760	1.538	1.400	1.273	1.207	1.104	1.070
Optimized 6D	1.859	2372.570	1.104	0.961	0.860	0.791	0.696	0.660	Optimized 6D	3.431	10022.990	1.484	1.392	1.273	1.220	1.106	1.069
Optimized 3D	2.207	2556.910	1.212	1.079	0.931	0.876	0.692	0.655	Optimized 3D	3.825	12786.940	1.618	1.472	1.357	1.269	1.123	1.068
2 frames (C-O)	1.981	2330.630	1.199	1.086	0.946	0.862	0.716	0.665									
2 frames (O-N)	2.029	2657.770	1.235	1.141	1.006	0.919	0.749	0.688									